

1	71.902771								
1.05	71.902771								
1.1	71.902771								
1.15	71.902771								
1.2	71.902771								
1.25	71.902771								
1.3	71.902771								
1.35	69.83734131								
1.4	69.83734131								
1.45	69.83734131								
1.5	69.83734131								
1.55	69.83734131								
1.6	69.83734131								
1.65	67.77191162								
1.7	67.77191162								
1.75	67.77191162								
1.8	67.77191162								
1.85	67.77191162								
1.9	67.77191162								
1.95	67.77191162								
2	67.77191162								
2.05	67.77191162								
2.1	67.77191162								
2.15	65.70648193								
2.2	65.70648193								
2.25	65.70648193								
2.3	65.70648193								
2.35	65.70648193								
2.4	65.70648193								
2.45	65.70648193								

2.5	65.70648193							
2.55	65.70648193							
2.6	65.70648193							
2.65	65.70648193							
2.7	65.70648193							
2.75	63.64105225							
2.8	65.70648193							
2.85	65.70648193							
2.9	65.70648193							
2.95	65.70648193							
3	65.70648193							
3.05	63.64105225							
3.1	63.64105225							
3.15	65.70648193							
3.2	65.70648193							
3.25	63.64105225							
3.3	63.64105225							
3.35	63.64105225							
3.4	65.70648193							
3.45	63.64105225							
3.5	65.70648193							
3.55	65.70648193							
3.6	65.70648193							
3.65	63.64105225							
3.7	65.70648193							
3.75	65.70648193							
3.8	65.70648193							
3.85	65.70648193							
3.9	65.70648193							
3.95	65.70648193							

4	65.70648193							
4.05	65.70648193							
4.1	65.70648193							
4.15	65.70648193							
4.2	65.70648193							
4.25	65.70648193							
4.3	65.70648193							
4.35	65.70648193							
4.4	65.70648193							
4.45	67.77191162							
4.5	67.77191162							
4.55	67.77191162							
4.6	67.77191162							
4.65	67.77191162							
4.7	67.77191162							
4.75	67.77191162							
4.8	67.77191162							
4.85	69.83734131							
4.9	69.83734131							
4.95	69.83734131							
5	69.83734131							
5.05	69.83734131							
5.1	69.83734131							
5.15	69.83734131							
5.2	69.83734131							
5.25	71.902771							
5.3	71.902771							
5.35	71.902771							
5.4	71.902771							
5.45	71.902771							

5.5	71.902771							
5.55	71.902771							
5.6	71.902771							
5.65	71.902771							
5.7	73.83911133							
5.75	73.83911133							
5.8	71.902771							
5.85	73.83911133							
5.9	73.83911133							
5.95	73.83911133							
6	73.83911133							
6.05	73.83911133							
6.1	75.90454102							
6.15	75.90454102							
6.2	75.90454102							
6.25	75.90454102							
6.3	75.90454102							
6.35	77.9699707							
6.4	75.90454102							
6.45	77.9699707							
6.5	77.9699707							
6.55	77.9699707							
6.6	77.9699707							
6.65	77.9699707							
6.7	77.9699707							
6.75	80.03540039							
6.8	80.03540039							
6.85	80.03540039							
6.9	80.03540039							
6.95	80.03540039							

7	80.03540039							
7.05	80.03540039							
7.1	80.03540039							
7.15	80.03540039							
7.2	80.03540039							
7.25	80.03540039							
7.3	82.10083008							
7.35	82.10083008							
7.4	82.10083008							
7.45	82.10083008							
7.5	82.10083008							
7.55	82.10083008							
7.6	84.16625977							
7.65	84.16625977							
7.7	84.16625977							
7.75	84.16625977							
7.8	84.16625977							
7.85	84.16625977							
7.9	84.16625977							
7.95	84.16625977							
8	84.16625977							
8.05	84.16625977							
8.1	86.23168945							
8.15	86.23168945							
8.2	86.23168945							
8.25	86.23168945							
8.3	86.23168945							
8.35	88.29711914							
8.4	88.29711914							
8.45	88.29711914							

8.5	88.29711914							
8.55	88.29711914							
8.6	88.29711914							
8.65	88.29711914							
8.7	90.36254883							
8.75	90.36254883							
8.8	90.36254883							
8.85	90.36254883							
8.9	90.36254883							
8.95	90.36254883							
9	90.36254883							
9.05	85.724242							
9.1	85.87462464							
9.15	86.02500728							
9.2	86.17538992							
9.25	86.32577256							
9.3	86.4761552							
9.35	86.62653784							
9.4	86.77692048							
9.45	86.92730312							
9.5	87.07768576							
9.55	87.22806841							
9.6	87.37845105							
9.65	87.52883369							
9.7	87.67921633							
9.75	87.82959897							
9.8	87.97998161							
9.85	88.13036425							
9.9	88.28074689							
9.95	88.43112953							

10	88.58151217							
----	-------------	--	--	--	--	--	--	--